

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BUX****FIRST NAME: PIR****PROGRAM CODE: DCSS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 06****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: %

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary purpose of an abstract in a research paper?
 - To summarize the main findings and conclusions.***¹
 - To provide a detailed literature review.
 - To list the references used in the paper.
 - To present alternative viewpoints on the topic.
2. When citing a book in a bibliography, which of the following elements is typically NOT included?

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 22.

Page numbers of the cited information.²

Title of the book.

Name of the author.

Place of publication.

3. Which of the following is NOT a recommended style for in-text citations in the Turabian format?

Parenthetical style.³

Author-date style.

Footnote style.

Endnote style.

Place of publication.

4. When should a researcher seek permission to use copyrighted materials in their thesis or dissertation?

Whenever using copyrighted materials, regardless of the amount used.⁴

Only when using materials published within the last five years.

Only when using large portions of the copyrighted materials.

Only when using materials from online sources.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 155.

³ Kate Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 167.

⁴ Ibid.

5. Which chapter of a qualitative dissertation typically introduces the research problem and research questions and provides an overview of the study?

Introduction.⁵

Literature Review.

Methodology.

Findings

6. Early stage of qualitative dissertation what is the purpose of conducting a literature review?

To provide a comprehensive summary of existing literature on the topic.⁶

To identify potential research participants.

To develop research questions and hypotheses.

To validate the research findings.

7. When developing a research proposal for a qualitative dissertation, what should be included in the methodology section?

Sampling technique and sample size justification.⁷

Detailed statistical analysis plan.

Pre-determined research outcomes.

Confirmation of hypothesis or research question.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 22.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Ibid.

8. Which of the following is an effective strategy for managing time and staying organized during the dissertation process?
- Creating a detailed project timeline and adhering to it.***⁸
 - Working on multiple tasks simultaneously.
 - Waiting for inspiration before starting work.
 - Ignoring distractions and focusing solely on the dissertation.
9. What is the purpose of conducting a pilot study before initiating the main qualitative research study?
- Ensuring voluntary participation and informed consent.***⁹
 - Altering research findings to fit preconceived notions.
 - Including only participants who share similar beliefs.
 - Limiting access to research data for other scholars.
10. Which of the following is an example of plagiarism in an essay?
- Without citing a source copying and pasting text.***¹⁰
 - Quoting a source directly and citing it properly.
 - Paraphrasing a source and citing it properly.
 - Summarizing a source without Citation Correct.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ *Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore Washington, DC Melbourne: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.